

AFFECTIVE TIMELINES TOWARDS THE PRIMARY-PROCESS EMOTIONS OF MOVIE WATCHERS: MEASUREMENTS BASED ON SELF- ANNOTATION AND AFFECTIVE NEUROSCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The economic success of a movie depends on audience satisfaction and on how much they are emotionally engaged while watching it. Our research is related to the identification of such kinds of emotions felt by movie watchers during screening movie. We endorse the model of 7 Primary-process emotions from Affective Neuroscience (SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, FEAR, GRIEF, RAGE and LUST) and ask subjects to watch 14 movies and match them with these 7 emotions. We provide a self-annotating application and reveal "Affective Timelines" of clicks with arousal scenes. We verify that it is possible to discriminate movie watchers' emotions according to their self-annotation by obtaining 0.51 - 0.81 range of accordance in annotating 14 movies and comparing them with the authors of this study. These timelines will be matched with physiological sensors in future research.

KEYWORDS: *Affect Annotation, Primary-process Emotions, Movie Watchers, Movie Analysis, Affective Computing.*

INTRODUCTION

Influencing the emotions is a key factor in satisfying a movie audience and for the overall success of the movie. Movies are art-forms that involve affective, perceptual and intellectual activity (Metz, 1991). Recent years demonstrate a growth in movie affective analysis. The field of affective multimedia content analysis demonstrates several methods to represent the range of emotions experienced by movie watchers (Kang, 2003; Hanjalic and Xu, 2005; Wang and Cheong, 2006; Arifin and Cheung, 2007; Xu, Jin and Luo, 2008; Zhang, Tian, Jiang and Huang, 2008; Zhang, Huang, Tian, Jiang and Gao, 2008). Studies in emotion tracking in movies show that most researchers focus on classifying large movie segments to a small number of distinct categories. In all cases, research has focused on narrow domains, such as specific movie genres, e.g. thrillers, cartoon for kids, love stories, and so on.

On the other hand, emotion tracking and annotation has gained popularity and has been used in numerous studies.

(Malandrakis et al, 2011) used supervised learning techniques for continuous time emotion tracking in movies for the first time. Their study used 12 30-minute movie clips where 7 volunteers had to annotate experienced emotions in a valence-

arousal scale by using the FEELTRACE (Cowie, 2000) emotion annotation tool. Participants viewed the films and, in real-time, annotated their emotional responses by moving the mouse pointer on a square two-dimensional area representing the valence-arousal emotional space. The results from their study contributed to a database of movie emotions in which the best emotion obtains over 50% for high arousal values.

A recent study by Zhang et al. used machine learning and algorithms to depict 13 arousal (e.g. music tempo) and 9 valence features (e.g. brightness) of 4000 movie segments. The performance of their algorithms was 60% accurate (Zhang et al. 2009).

In terms of visualization, there has been an increase in visualizing movie emotions due to increasing movie production. In general, scholars wish to facilitate movie browsing by categorizing their prevailing emotions. In one of their research papers, the scholars proposed the iFelt web interface system (Oliveira, 2011) and in particular, the Emotional Wheel, to catalog, access, browse and visualize movies and movie scenes based on participants' emotional properties and impact. Her study used 10 participants and found that 90% of subjects were visibly enjoying the exploration of timelines. This study inspired us to further pursue how to visualize the emotions.

Emotions captured from facial expressions can be seen in studies with 90% successful tracking (McDuff, El Kaliouby, and Picard, 2011). Their study used a corpora and made it plausible to match emotions for more than 290 videos.

This research was based mostly on short movie scenes shown for the participants in single screenings. Also, most of the research was based on diverse models such as arousal-valence and basic emotions model proposed by Ekman (1992) - happiness, sadness, surprise, fear, anger and disgust. These emotions are used both in movie contents and on users' annotated emotions. To the best of our knowledge, to date, no studies have been undertaken based on an Affective Neuroscience model and involving affective annotations. Our study will use users' annotation in the quest for Primary-process emotions in movie watchers.

In general, the question of how emotions should be modeled is still being contested. Researchers commonly accept the AV (arousal/valence) model. Besides the importance of two-dimensional emotional analysis, our paper is based on modeling proposed by Affective Neuroscience due to its rigorous approach in identifying key emotions. Namely, an internal status of all mammals is a way to increase the survival capacity during the species' evolution and only 7 emotional systems can be recognized: SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, LUST, FEAR, GRIEF and RAGE. In particular, Panksepp (1998) measured and clinically verified these emotions to specific neurotransmitters, exact brain areas and behaviors. Notably, in his research, Ekman's proposed that the emotion "surprise" has not been identified at all as an emotion. Although characterization of emotions by physiological patterns still has some limitations regarding the differentiation of emotions from physiological signals (Rainville et al. 2006), we embrace this model as an intrinsic one as Panksepp argues that emotions are all subcortical (Panksepp, 2010). We can suppose that the neocortex will play a key role in the interpretation of emotions by different cultures and diverse ethical standards; however, these 7 basic emotions are the same across all mammals. The focus of this study will not be on time-consuming neuroscientific analysis. Our aim is to set up a benchmark of Primary-process emotions in movies, which will be evaluated with physiological sensors in future

studies. Further, we contribute with the usage of full-length movies for the purpose of allowing more natural timing for experiencing specific emotions. We should point out that our research also includes categorical labeling for the classification of both movie scenes as well as for a person's self annotation moments in time. However, we believe that our future studies will improve with the differentiation of emotions from physiological signals.

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we explain the (i) establishment of our ground truth - how we create a benchmark of emotions; and (ii) application setup (used to measure emotions felt by movie watchers and compared with authors' emotion agreement).

Establishing the Ground Truth

The analysis was carried out in a multicultural environment with researchers from Serbia (male), Iran (female) and Italy (male). Our study analyzed 16 movies, of which 2 were discarded due to the disagreement among authors (several scenes showed opposite emotions of a kind - e.g. CARE/GRIEF). This left 14 movies for analysis. We categorized movies according to our assumption that a movie can have one prevailing emotion (Table 1).

Two authors watched all movies and had the task to assign emotions which were felt during each scene. For each movie, we extracted scenes according to normal changes in the film (e.g. change of surrounding, a dialogue that evolves into a fight, etc.). For each scene, we extracted the length of seconds and assigned to it a prevailed emotion that each author felt (e.g. for a scene where a couple is passionately kissing, authors most probably annotated the scene as LUST). At the end of scene annotation, authors compared their results and verified the accordance rate expressed in mean value. Our threshold was that each author had the same or same kind of emotion assigned per scene (e.g. either both PLAY, or one PLAY and the other CARE which could be matched as they are both positive emotions).

Figure 1. Mean value and authors' accordance of felt emotion per scene.
Movie: Nine 1/2 Weeks by Adrian Lyne. With Mickey Rourke, Kim Basinger (1986)

DOMINANT EMOTION HYPOTHESIS	TITLE	DURATION	TOTAL SCENES	MAX SCENE DURATION	AVERAGE SCENE DURATION
SEEKING	Psycho	1:48:25	59	0:07:26	0:01:52
SEEKING	Birds	1:54:36	113	0:04:25	0:01:00
PLAY	Singin' in the Rain	1:42:39	97	0:05:14	0:01:04
PLAY	Bambi	1:07:40	43	0:06:39	0:01:34
CARE	Pretty Woman	1:59:37	78	0:07:51	0:01:30
CARE	I am Sam	2:12:18	116	0:04:58	0:01:07
FEAR	Night of the Living Dead	1:32:42	57	0:07:01	0:01:43
FEAR	Saw	1:43:12	66	0:04:35	0:01:33
GRIEF	Bitter Moon	2:19:05	104	0:03:59	0:01:21
GRIEF	Dancer in the Dark	2:14:27	94	0:06:15	0:01:27
RAGE	Incident	1:39:31	40	0:35:50	0:02:24
RAGE	Schindler's List	3:06:54	183	0:05:06	0:01:02
LUST	9 1/2 Weeks	1:57:03	91	0:04:43	0:01:18
LUST	Blue is the Warmest Color	2:52:57	106	0:07:57	0:01:39
	sum	28:11:06	1247	Mean	0:01:28
	avg	2:00:48	89	-1sd	0:01:05
				+sd	0:01:51

Table 1. Total annotated movies performed by Authors (2) and Subjects (1 main +3 appearing in three sole movies)

A typical example of authors' agreement can be seen in Figure 1. In this particular movie, we observe an "Affective Timeline" where the X axis is the sequence of scenes (same length) and the Y axis is the intensity (scenes calculated in seconds). This suggests that the higher the peak, the longer the scene and that a specific scene presented an unambiguous emotion.

In the next step, we categorized movies into 3 types:

- **Unequivocal Emotion Movie** - a movie in which a single emotion is dominant above all other emotions. Our thresholds were that the average agreement rate among all authors with respect to: a) a prevalence of any emotion above SEEKING; b) a prevailing emotion has to be at least 50% higher in intensity than other emotions (excluding SEEKING). A typical example can be observed in the figures below. This chart depicts the prevalence of PLAY on SEEKING by more than 30% (as well as more than 50% on CARE, RAGE and LUST emotions found in this movie). In this case, GRIEF, FEAR and a neutral state were considered marginal by all authors as they did not appear in the scenes throughout the movie at all.

Figure 2. PLAY - Singing in the Rain by Stanley Donen.

With Gene Kelly, Donald O'Connor (1952)

Figure 3. RAGE - The Incident by Larry Peerce.

With Victor Arnold, Robert Bannard (1967)

Figure 4. GRIEF - Dancer in the Dark by Lars von Trier. With Björk, Catherine Deneuve (2000)

Figure 5. PLAY - Bambi by James Algar. With Hardie Albright, Stan Alexander (1942)

Figure 6. CARE - I am Sam by Jessie Nelson. With Sean Penn, Michelle Pfeiffer (2001)

Figure 7. FEAR - Night of the Living Dead by George A. Romero. With Duane Jones, Judith O'Dea, Karl Hardman (1968)

- Bridging Emotion Movie** - SEEKING is used to trigger other dominant emotions. Our threshold was similar to the previous case where the prevailing emotions should be 50% more intense than other emotions. A typical example is depicted in Figure 10 below. It is clear to note the dominance of GRIEF on other emotions. We believe that SEEKING in this movie was mostly used to correlate with GRIEF. This is in accordance with Panksepp's argument (Panksepp, 2010) that SEEKING is the mother of all emotions and can be used to trigger all remaining ones. We should note an exception, that although the authors' agreement rate for movie number 11 (see Table 1) is mainly GRIEF, we consider this movie LUST-dominant because it contained a higher number of scenes of sexual activity than scenes with notable grief.
- Two of a Kind Emotion Movie** (including SEEKING and two major dominant emotions). Our threshold was again as in previous cases that a prevailed emotion should be 50% higher in intensity than other emotions. An example can be seen in Figures 14 and 15 below. FEAR and GRIEF are indeed dominant over other emotions where SEEKING was used to augment or diminish FEAR and GRIEF scenes.

Figure 8. LUST - Nine 1/2 Weeks by Adrian Lyne. With Mickey Rourke, Kim Basinger (1986)

Figure 9. CARE - Pretty Woman. Directed by Garry Marshall. With Richard Gere, Julia Roberts (1990)

Figure 10. GRIEF - Bitter Moon by Roman Polanski. With Hugh Grant, Kristin Scott Thomas (1992)

Figure 11. FEAR - Psycho by by Alfred Hitchcock. With Anthony Perkins, Janet Leigh, Vera Miles (1960)

Figure 12. FEAR - Birds by Alfred Hitchcock. With Rod Taylor, Tippi Hedren, Suzanne Pleshette (1963)

Figure 13. LUST - Blue is the Warmest Color by Abdellatif Kechiche. With Léa Seydoux, Adèle Exarchopoulos, Salim Kechiouche (2013)

Figure 14. FEAR-GRIEF - Saw by James Wan. With Cary Elwes, Leigh Whannell (2004)

Figure 15. GRIEF-RAGE - Schindler's List by Steven Spielberg. With Liam Neeson, Ralph Fiennes, Ben Kingsley (1993)

Application Setup

To verify our ground truth, we designed and developed a desktop (Win 32, used in research) and mobile (Android, in progress) application - available at <http://siplab.org/Emotions.rar> - and instructed the movie watcher in how to use them. Throughout the present research, subjects used only the desktop application which was switched on next to the window with movie. The main motivation in designing this

application was to try to collect self-annotated emotions as unobtrusively as possible so participants could be enjoying the movie as much as possible. Below are examples of the application's user interfaces.

Subjects were clicking on emotions during 14 movies.

Our main movie watcher was a 29 year-old Polish female who was fond of movies. She was provided with an explanation of the definition of 7 Primary-process emotions followed by an

example. Further, we demonstrated how to use the application by performing basic tests such as reset function, seeing the statistics, finding the location of data file, etc. We instructed the movie watcher to click/tap on an emotion when she felt one while watching of the movie. Total screening time was around 28 hours. The same steps were performed with another 3 participants (from Lebanon, Serbia and Italy), who watched Psycho, Bambi, Dancer in the Dark and Blue is the Warmest Color.

Figure 16. UI Main interface while watching the movie, UI Stats interface with real-time annotations and UI reset page

RESULTS

DOMINANT EMOTION HYPOTHESIS	TITLE	SEEN BEFORE?	SEEKING	PLAY	CARE	FEAR	GRIEF	RAGE	LUST	CLICK AGREE
			(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)
SEEKING	Psycho	no	0.81	-	-	0.18			0.01	0.68
SEEKING	Birds	yes	0.72	-	0.12	0.16	-	-	-	0.75
PLAY	Singin' in the Rain	yes	0.06	0.80	0.02	-	-	-	0.12	0.75
PLAY	Bambi	no	0.21	0.43	0.19	0.13	-	-	0.04	0.64
CARE	Pretty Woman	yes	0.50	0.26	0.16	0.01	-	0.03	0.04	0.69
CARE	I am Sam	no	0.14	0.14	0.53	0.03	0.12	0.03	-	0.52
FEAR	Night of the Living Dead	no	0.44	-	-	0.54	-	0.02	-	0.51
FEAR	Saw	no	0.58	-	0.04	0.38	-	-	-	0.58
GRIEF	Bitter Moon	no	0.72	0.08	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.59
GRIEF	Dancer in the Dark	yes	0.71	0.11	0.12	0.02	0.04	-	-	0.52
RAGE	Incident	yes	0.79	-	0.10	0.06	-	0.05	-	0.81
RAGE	Schindler's List	no	0.80	0.01	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.74
LUST	9 1/2 Weeks	yes	0.51	0.32	0.03	0.03	0.01	-	0.11	0.80
LUST	Blue is the Warmest Color	no	0.59	0.19	0.17	-	-	-	0.04	0.74

Table 2. Which emotions are clicked the most (a-g) by subject? Do clicked emotions fall onto equal emotion annotation by authors (h)?

Below is a representation of the movie watchers' clicks (colors) against our annotation (gray) agreement per movie (see Establishing the Ground Truth). The question was how far does the movie watcher agree with the authors?

In what we consider an overall observation of all movies which were self-annotated by our subject movie watchers, GRIEF, surprisingly, demonstrated significant decline and LUST does not exceed the PLAY emotion. In general, PLAY Unequivocal Movie Emotions and their scenes are usually depicted with dancing and music. CARE, on the other hand, is usually recognized by a dialogue between two persons. What we learn is that: When a movie is interesting it has lot of clicks and SEEKING. CARE is substitute for RAGE and GRIEF scenes. PLAY, CARE and FEAR when present, dominate SEEKING. Also, we believe that clicking on these emotions was, in some cases,

die to a neocortical processing e.g. subject had tears in their eyes in the closing scenes of Schindler's Lists; but they annotated SEEKING. Also, in very scary scenes as in The Night of the Living Dead, the clicking came a couple of seconds after the scream.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we focus on understanding the emotions of movie watchers. We endorse 7 Primary-process emotions depicted in Affective Neuroscience and use their definition of emotions. We endow a ground truth by analyzing 14 movies and assigning a single emotion per scene according to the emotion we believe we felt while watching a movie. We cre-

Figure 17 (a). Subject and authors' agreement for 12 MOVIES
 7 - SEEKING, 6 - PLAY, 5 - CARE, 4 - FEAR, 3 - GRIEF, 2 - RAGE, 1 - LUST
 gray color - authors, other colors - subject 1, black dots - subject 2
 height - intensity of clicks per scene

Figure 17 (b). Subject and authors' agreement for 12 MOVIES
 7 - SEEKING, 6 - PLAY, 5 - CARE, 4 - FEAR, 3 - GRIEF, 2 - RAGE, 1 - LUST
 gray color - authors, other colors - subject 1, black dots - subject 2
 height - intensity of clicks per scene

ate "Affective Timelines" for each movie, which we use as a benchmark in comparison with emotions annotated by the movie watcher. Further, a desktop and mobile application was designed, developed and provided to the movie watcher. Next, we explained to we explained the main definition of 7 emotions and explained the usage of the application. We asked participants to annotate emotions by clicking on prevailing ones felt while watching the movie. Once a movie is finished, software provides statistics and movie watchers can observe their percentage of assigned emotion in the movie. After that, the movie watchers were asked to choose the main emotion that for them describes the movie. Participants provided the feedback to the research authors for further analysis and comparison. Our results found that an agreement varies between 0.51 - 0.81 among authors and movie watcher (see Table 2, "click agree" column). Obviously, our research has to consider several limitations:

Neuroscience measurements. It is worth mentioning that our model stands on Primary-process emotions which are presented by the research in Affective Neuroscience. We focus solely on 7 emotions (SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, LUST, FEAR, GRIEF and RAGE) as they are proven to exist in all mammals and were measured in exact brain areas and neurotransmitters. We are aware that we are not able to obtain exact fMRI scans and to verify the true measurements of participants' emotions during the movie watching. However, our future study will evolve physiological responses and measurements of movie watchers (heart rate, skin conductivity, etc.).

Specimen issue. Although 14 movies were used for data acquisition, the results of this study should be considered as preliminary as they do not contain a bountiful number of subjects (less than 10 movie watcher analyses per movie). However, we expect that a future analysis with a greater sample will demonstrate more significant results.

Multicultural difficulty of research. We should take into consideration that the research was conducted in multicultural setting as participants and authors were from 4 different European and Middle-Eastern countries. However, our hypothesis in research is that Primary-process emotions are same across all cultures (excluding the neo-cortex interpretations) and we believe that we are able to show the preliminary emotions whit respect to the cultural origin. More subjects of diverse cultures are needed and will be the focus of future research.

Technological constraints. We should also take into account the designed and developed application. Namely, it could be supposed that there is a nuance in performance during the affect annotation. This hinders the synchronization of the movie and the movie watcher's affect timelines. We could therefore assume a tolerance of +/- 3%. In this research, we created an application and tried to use a natural surrounding for movie watching so that the watchers' level of immersion remains a priority.

Non-referenced attributes. Future study also involves the detailed analysis of perceptual elements (such are soundtrack,

color, shots, plot, etc.) that we believe are able to determine specific emotions in the watchers. We could classify movie genres according to these emotions and present emotional characteristics in percentages for each movie type: thrillers, cartoons for kids, love stories, and so on. Our ongoing study also involves the verification of the emotional "footprint" of famous directors, e.g. Hitchcock and his art of creating suspense (Truffaut, 1985).

Interpretations versus Primary-process emotions. In this research, we also used a categorical labeling of emotions, which might be a subject of neo-cortical interpretation. Although Ekman proposes Anger, while Panksepp proposes RAGE, we are still at the beginning when it comes to understanding Primary-process emotions. We believe that by setting up this benchmark (highest possible agreement among authors and movie watchers), it will provide us with insight into these emotions which will be compared against their physiological measurements. We are also aware that there are differences when focusing on two actors in the scene. One actor might be stimulating RAGE in the watcher, while the other may be inspiring CARE. We can conclude that more subjects are needed for more precise results.

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